

Table 1: Communication domain.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
DC1	Deficient communication during development activities, resulting in delays and increased time to complete technical tasks, which negatively impacts source code quality [P4, P7, P15, P16, P19, P20, P23, P26, P28, P29, P32, P34 – P47].
DC2	Differences in perception between technical and organizational roles—such as managers and developers—regarding technical debt management [P4, P11, P22, P41, P44, P45].
DC3	Lack of clarity and understanding of information, often caused by communication failures from leadership to technical teams [P3, P4, P23, P25, P41].
DC4	Collaboration without message exchange—developers working independently without maintaining effective communication [P7, P28, P41, P45].
DC5	Limited stakeholder participation [P16, P41].
DC6	Lack of consensus in technical decision-making [P4, P28, P41].
DC7	Poor or absent feedback [P2, P4, P7, P28].
DC8	Lack of social interaction and developer isolation, which weakens team cohesion and hinders informal knowledge sharing [P2, P4, P7, P41].
DC9	Poorly managed asynchronous communication, leading to information loss, misunderstandings, and delays—especially in distributed or remote contexts [P2, P4, P26, P28, P41].
DC10	Omission of meetings, reducing opportunities for progress sharing and conflict resolution [P2, P4, P41].
DC11	Cognitive errors and information loss in communication chains, distorting knowledge transmission [P2–P4, P7, P41].
DC12	Lack of explicit communication regarding organizational norms, structures, and responsibilities, leading to confusion and task duplication [P3, P4, P41].
DC13	Work overload that limits effective communication [P4].
DC14	Communication challenges derived from software architecture, such as module or package dependencies [P4].
DC15	Technical debt acting as a barrier to effective communication and trust-building [P3].
DC16	Intercultural communication issues, arising from language barriers, differing communication styles, and lack of leadership [P2, P5].
DC17	Low-quality communication, characterized by commanding expressions, lack of courtesy, poor emotional regulation, or the use of inadequate informal channels [P2].

Collaboration and social structure are essential domains in software development; however, when these are poorly manifested, they can act as generators of SD. Such conditions negatively affect collaboration among team members, reduce productivity, hinder task execution, limit the sharing of knowledge and responsibilities, and ultimately compromise the quality of the final software product [? ?]. The main causes and suboptimal patterns associated with this factor, which contribute to the accumulation of SD, are presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Collaboration and Social Structure domain.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
DCE1	Unresolved conflicts between team members that deteriorate trust [P1, P2, P7, P28, P34, P41, P42, P43, P45, P47].
DCE2	Lack of transparency in knowledge sharing [P2, P7, P8, P28, P34, P39–P43, P45, P47].

DCE3	Dominant participation by individuals with strong personalities [P1, P28, P34, P41, P45].
DCE4	Absence of social ties between developers working on shared tasks [P1, P2, P7, P28, P34, P39, P45, P47].
DCE5	Poor collaboration due to a lack of psychological safety and inclusive leadership that fosters active participation [P1, P2, P28, P34, P41].
DCE6	“Lone wolf” behavior, exemplified by developers who focus solely on their own code without contributing to integration efforts [P7, P8, P28, P34, P39, P41, P45, P47].
DCE7	Presence of fragmented and inflexible social structures [P7, P8, P28, P34, P35, P39–P43, P45, P46].
DCE8	Fragmented social networks among developers that hinder team cohesion [P7, P28, P34, P35, P39, P41, P45–P47].
DCE9	Limited collaboration resulting from misalignment between project governance and product vision [P2, P28, P34, P41, P42, P43, P47].
DCE10	Poorly defined architectural roles and inequitable distribution of responsibilities [P8, P28, P34, P39, P41, P42, P43, P47].
DCE11	Homogeneous organizational structures that promote rigid social patterns and short-term thinking [P28, P34, P41].
DCE12	Fragile structures vulnerable to staff turnover and poor scalability [P1, P7, P28, P41, P47].
DCE13	Incorrect structural decisions impacting team coordination [P8, P28, P34, P39, P41, P42, P43, P45, P46].
DCE14	Presence of antisocial behaviors within the team [P2, P28, P34, P41].
DCE15	Existence of organizational anti-patterns such as fear, isolation, and excessive bureaucracy [P1, P7, P28, P39, P41, P47].

Acronyms used: Domain of collaboration and social structure (DCE).

On the other hand, the domain of work coordination is particularly relevant, as it involves the organization and interdependence of tasks, resources, roles, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure the efficient and coherent execution of activities aimed at achieving project objectives. Deficiencies in this domain—especially within distributed teams—can lead to the accumulation of SD, misalignment of efforts, and divergence from project goals [?], [?].The main identified causes are presented Table 3.

Table 3: Coordination domain.

Id	Cause and primary studies
DCO1	Inadequate management of inter-task dependencies [P1–P33].
DCO2	Lack of clear distribution of responsibilities, poorly defined roles, and tasks assigned to a limited number of team members without redundancy [P1–P33].
DCO3	Excessive pressure creating bottlenecks [P1–P47].
DCO4	Lack of coordination between teams due to unshared technical decisions [P1–P47].
DCO5	Coordination difficulties in multi-team environments, often caused by poor communication [P1–P47].
DCO6	Lack of adequate iterative planning [P3, P4].
DCO7	Lack of coordination between processes and roles, resulting in uncontrolled dependencies [P1–P47].

DCO8	Informal coordination among architects, developers, and clients [P2–P47].
DCO9	Challenges caused by frequent reorganizations or weak agile coordination structures [P2–P47].
DCO10	Bottlenecks caused by the concentration of responsibilities in individual leaders [P1–P47].
DCO11	Unreported changes leading to inconsistencies [P1–P47].
DCO12	Poor coordination due to structural differences, geographical distance, and time zone misalignment [P1–P47].
DCO13	Lack of structured coordination due to implicit governance, with no clear rules or established processes [P1–P47].
DCO14	Excessive procedural burden and lack of process clarity [P1–P47].
DCO15	Low team cohesion and misalignment of roles [P1–P47].
DCO16	Lack of gender diversity associated with poor coordination dynamics [P1–P45].
DCO17	Parallel software development without communication among developers [P1–P47].
DCO18	Lack of mechanisms for sharing architectural responsibilities across roles [P1–P47].
DCO19	Inconsistent assignment of teams and roles, resulting from poorly defined organizational structures [P1–P47].
DCO20	Low socio-technical congruence [P1–P47].
DCO21	Negative emotional states or prolonged stress [P1–P47].
DCO22	Filtered interactions and communication delays due to fear of sharing critical information [P1–P47].
DCO23	Changes in work routines and increased isolation among team members [P1–P47].

Acronyms used: Domain Coordination (DCO).

Likewise, relevant causes associated with the domain of socio-technical congruence were identified Table 4. This domain focuses on the alignment between social and technical factors in software development, where adequate correspondence enables the assessment of coordination levels and the identification of gaps that may lead to delays, compromise project outcomes, or—under critical conditions—result in project failure [? ?].

Table 4: Socio-technical Congruence domain.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
DCS1	Presence of the phenomenon known as obfuscated architecture, which arises when multiple subgroups emerge within a development network without a unified organizational and socio-technical vision. This impairs mutual understanding and hinders effective architectural communication [P4, P5].
DCS2	Imbalance in the architect’s role, who must mediate between proposed technical solutions and the social and organizational challenges within the team [P3, P9].
DCS3	Deficiency in socio-technical congruence, understood as the lack of alignment between technical dependencies and social coordination mechanisms, which can negatively affect both software productivity and quality [P3, P6].
DCS4	Suboptimal interaction between architects, Product Owners, and development teams, resulting in architectural decisions that are disconnected from actual customer needs [P42].
DCS5	Deficient socio-technical structures that hinder the creation of a cohesive work environment between technical and organizational components, thereby generating social debt [P9].

Acronyms used: Socio-Technical Congruence Domain (STC).

In addition, another domain addressed involves cultural and organizational factors (see Table 5), which may contribute to the emergence of SD when organizations experience situations such as:

Table 5: Cultural and organizational factors Domain.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
DFC1	Absence of values and norms aligned with organizational objectives [P2].
DFC2	Poor interaction among team members [P2].
DFC3	Reduced communication leading to misunderstandings and misalignment with project and organizational goals [P2].
DFC4	Social distance resulting from rigid organizational hierarchies [P5].
DFC5	Avoidance of scheduled meetings [P2].
DFC6	Structural and cultural barriers such as geographical distance, language differences, time zone gaps, and cultural diversity [P22].
DFC7	Absence of diversity-aware organizational policies [P12].
DFC8	Lack of shared norms to guide team member interactions [P28].
DFC9	Organizational or individual resistance to change [P5].
DFC10	Excess or lack of organizational formality [P5].
DFC11	Power structures or informal hierarchies that hinder participation [P41].
DFC12	Unequal perceptions regarding the importance of gender diversity [P12].
DFC13	Implicit, non-explicit hierarchies [P44].
DFC14	Non-participatory, individualistic, or weak organizational cultures [P3].
DFC15	Managers' lack of understanding of team culture, which prevents inclusive management [P3].
DFC16	Low investment in essential human resources functions such as talent development, integration, and retention [P3].
DFC17	Recruitment errors that worsen cultural incompatibility and hinder new member integration [P3].
DFC18	Linguistic distance and unmanaged cultural diversity [P22].
DFC19	Organizational heterogeneity stemming from divergent cultural norms and values [P28].
DFC20	Lack of intercultural awareness and absence of mediating figures [P22].
DFC21	Organizational cultures that prioritize factors such as experience or team size over inclusion [P12].
DFC22	Lack of recognition or organizational support for team members [P3].
DFC23	Ongoing tensions between sub-teams caused by cultural, technical, or structural differences [P28].
DFC24	Unstable processes and poor decision-making [P28].
DFC25	Individualistic work culture [P3].

Acronyms used: Domain Cultural and Organizational Factor (DFC).

As a complement to the analysis conducted, the domains that most significantly contribute to the generation of social debt (SD) were identified, based on findings reported in primary studies. The domain with the highest incidence was communication, present in 39 studies (40%), due to its critical role in business understanding, team interaction, knowledge transfer,

and the development of collaborative environments. Issues such as information silos, radio silence, and poor feedback mechanisms underscore its pivotal role as a source of SD.

Coordination and cultural and organizational factors followed closely, each cited in 35 studies (36%). The former is associated with inconsistent decision-making and lack of follow-up, while the latter involves institutional norms, leadership styles, cultural differences, and hierarchical structures that influence team dynamics. Lastly, collaboration and social structure appeared in 33 studies (34%), highlighting environments marked by isolated roles, limited cooperation, and high power distance.

These findings highlight the need to develop both social and technical skills, establish clear organizational structures, and foster a culture of coordination, collaboration, and continuous improvement—particularly in distributed settings and agile methodologies.